

AN *IN SITU* STUDY OF FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH IN COMRAL-85 AT AMBIENT AND ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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SUMMARY: Direct observation of the interaction of a fatigue crack with the microstructure and reinforcement in Comral-85 metal matrix composite (MMC) at both ambient and elevated temperatures was undertaken. In general particle matrix debonding was the dominant mechanism and is explained in terms of the constraint imposed by the particles on the matrix. Prior to failure the process zone, consisting of debonded particles and microcracked matrix, around and in front of the crack tip increased. There was still little evidence of cracked particles although some became evident. The major growth mechanism was the linkage of debonded particles by the crack growing through the matrix. There was also evidence of the crack seeking particle clusters due to the significant debonding occurring in these regions.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composite, fatigue, in-situ, crack growth

INTRODUCTION

There has been a considerable amount of investigation into the fatigue behaviour of metal matrix composites (MMCs). Characterisation of the behaviour through S-N curves and crack growth data have been the main areas of research. A number of mechanisms have been observed during fatigue crack propagation. Possible reinforcement-crack tip interactions during fatigue crack growth are particle fracture promoted by coarse particles in high strength matrices; the crack remaining in the matrix promoted by strong interfaces and high modulus particles; crack growth along particle-matrix interfaces promoted by weak interfaces (precipitation, oxidation, reaction).

These crack growth mechanisms have generally been determined from post mortem studies of the fracture surface or thin slices taken perpendicular to the crack plane.. In this study the crack growth mechanisms were observed *in situ*.

Shang and Ritchie have suggested the dominant mechanisms, near threshold, that lead to better fatigue crack growth resistance involve crack deflection around particles and crack trapping by the particles with the composites of coarser particles being the most effective at higher crack growth rates. Shang et al. found that with increasing K levels in the intermediate regime, growth rates become progressively slower in the composites, particularly in the coarse SiCp material compared with the unreinforced alloys. This was the result of a mutual

competition of SiC particle fracture ahead of the crack-tip (enhancing crack growth) and crack bridging from ligaments behind the crack-tip (retarding crack growth).

The effect was more pronounced with the large SiC particles as they are more effective in bridging. As the stress intensities approached K_{IC} the growth rates were found to be higher in both composites compared with the unreinforced alloy due to their much lower fracture toughness. Shang et al. concluded that the fracture crack growth performance of the system studied depends upon the interaction, and in particular the brittle fracture of the SiC particles. The interaction was found to vary with stress intensity level and the size of the carbides.

For many composites the fracture of particles ahead of the crack tip has been given as a reason for enhanced crack growth rates. For very strong or very fine reinforcements this acceleration mechanism is not relevant as little or no particle fracture occurs. Knowles and King have suggested, for these materials, an acceleration mechanism associated with failure at or near the particle-matrix interface.

Factors such as highly faceted crack growth which can lead to crack closure would not be applicable for fine grain size composites. The high dislocation densities associated with the thermal expansion mismatch in MMCs and the closely spaced reinforcements all act to homogenise slip, even in under-aged matrices. As well, the presence of the particles has been shown to accelerate the ageing process in some systems and to cause an increase in precipitate density near the particle reinforcement.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material used in this study was Comral-85, a spherical ceramic particle (20 vol.%) reinforced 6061 aluminium alloy composite. The composite is produced via the liquid metallurgy route by Comalco Research Centre.

The specimens tested were small compact tension specimens, 20 X 20 mm by 3mm thick and heat treated to the T6 condition. The specimens were polished, ion etched and pre-cracked in a laboratory machine at $6 < \Delta K < 10 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. Cracks were grown on a small servo-hydraulic machine outside the SEM. The specimen was then introduced into the microscope chamber in a special loading rig and cycled at rates from 0.3 to 1Hz, at an $R=0.1$ and an initial ΔK of $8.5 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. The crack tip region of each specimen was observed and photographed with both video film and still photographs. In order to save wear and tear on the fixture and to allow interactions to be studied at increasing K levels the specimen was removed, at required intervals, from the SEM and cycled outside on the servo-hydraulic and then replaced in the chamber for further observation. A similar loading stage, but with heating facilities, was used for the elevated temperature experiments.

The deformation response of the material in the crack tip zone was first determined by observing stereo pairs of the crack tip in the loaded and unloaded conditions. Some of the displacements visualised in the stereo-viewer were measured using DISMAP, an automated analysis system. From the measured displacements, three elements of the symmetric strain tensor (ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} , γ_{xy}) were computed at each measurement point, using the large strain definition, and from these values, the principal strains, the maximum shear strain and the mean and effective strains were derived. Thus eight values of strain were obtained at each of the ≈ 40 to 200 points within each field examined.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In all cases studied the major crack growth mechanism was one of particle-matrix debonding ahead of the crack tip followed by linkage to the main crack. Particle cracking ahead of the crack tip that was evident in fast fracture experiments was not observed except at ΔK approaching K_{IC} .

Ambient Temperature Tests

Debonding was not limited to interfaces perpendicular to the applied load and was observed on interfaces parallel to the loading direction. For example, the large particle at centre bottom in Figure 1 is debonded at the top interface. This is particularly clear when viewed stereoscopically. Where debonding occurs on any particle is a function of the relative orientation of the approaching crack tip. For example, the particle at the top of the photograph is debonded on the right hand side a result of the approach of the crack towards that side.

Figure 1. Comral-85 at $\Delta K \approx 10 \text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ after (a) 48,000, (b) 53,000, (c) 57,000 and (d) 59,500 cycles.

The rate of crack growth was also found to vary depending on the vicinity of the crack tip to the particles. As the crack negotiated a path around the particles the crack growth rate was seen to decrease. For the case of Figure 1(d) the crack growth rate was seen to reduce as the particle approached the top of the particle. In general it was observed in going around particles

the crack provided crack surfaces at orientations up to 90° to the applied load reducing the effective driving force at the crack tip. Also significant Mode II displacement was observed. The sliding surfaces and the presence of the particles behind the crack tip also provided a wedging action on the crack, the crack opening displacement being observed to be quite large even when the crack tip in front of these disturbances were tightly shut.

The particle on the very left in Figure 1(a) is debonded, visible clearly when viewed stereographically, some 18µm ahead of the effective crack tip. The crack does eventually link up with this particle and can be seen to be “opening up” in Figure 1(b). Evidence of the crack growing parallel to the applied load is seen in Figure 1(c). An estimation of the crack growth rate from the video is approximately 4×10^{-9} m/cycle at a ΔK of 8MPa√m. This corresponds well with values obtained from standard crack growth measurements. Debonding was not limited to one particle near the crack tip.

As the crack grew the incidence of debonding and microcracking in the matrix, along grain boundaries between particles, increased occurring further away from the crack tip as the stress intensity range increased. Growth, then occurs, by a mechanism by which these microcracks and debonds linked up. Crack branching was also observed and seemed to occur at grain boundary intersections. These branches generally only grew a small distance, however, some vied with the main crack for some distance growing at the same rate. In all cases the main crack continued to propagate, the branches slowing down and stopping.

Prior to failure the process zone around the crack tip, consisting of debonded particles and microcracked matrix, increased. The number of particles that started to crack also increased. There was also evidence of the crack seeking particle clusters due to the significant debonding occurring in these regions. Figure 2 shows some of these effects.

Figure 2. Comral-85 specimen at $\Delta K \approx 12 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ after 66,500 cycles outside the SEM and (a) 100 cycles in the SEM and (b) 200 cycles inside the SEM.

Figure 2(a) shows the crack passing along the right side of the particle. Close examination of the video and the photograph via stereoscopic techniques shows that crack branching, along grain boundaries, has occurred. ('1', '2' & '3' in Figure 2b). Large shear deformation was observed. On cycling the microcrack near the bottom of the particle (3 in Figure 2) won out.

Over the next 100 cycles damage accumulation continued between the particle at the top of the figure and the two joined particles in the centre of the photograph. Figure 2(b) shows the crack growing via the linkage of debonds and cracking along grain boundaries.

Over the 100 cycles the crack had now joined the two particles. ΔK was now increased by 2 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. At lower magnifications a large degree of debonding was now observed around the crack tip. On reaching the joined particles the crack branched again. Crack opening displacement $2\mu\text{m}$ behind the crack tip was now measured at $10\mu\text{m}$. Microcracking along grain boundaries continued with these microcracks growing in both directions and linking up to form the dominant crack.

With the formation of this deformation zone of debonding and microcracks the crack opening increased dramatically, as shown in Figure 3, and is primarily a result of the large horizontal section of the crack that was the crack branch through the “joint” in the two particles.

Figure 3. Comral-85 after 66,500 cycles outside the SEM and 400 cycles in the chamber.

Debonding and microcracking can be seen clearly in Figure 3, highlighted by the edge effects or charging in the photograph. The deformation zone is becoming quite large with cracking occurring predominantly at particle agglomerations. Significant debonding occurs at particle agglomerates ahead of the main crack tip. This debonded region then links up with the crack tip resulting in an effective sudden increase in crack length. Of course the effective crack tip in a system like this is very difficult to determine. Significant Mode II displacement is also observed as is large deformation within the matrix and wedging some $100\mu\text{m}$ behind the main crack tip. As failure approaches slip line formation and shear bands are observed as is the classic sharpening/blunting cycle (over approximately 3-4 cycles)

Elevated Temperature Tests

At 180°C similar trends are observed with intergranular crack growth much more pronounced. Grain boundaries parallel to the applied load slide over one another slowing down the local crack growth rate until the deformation in the matrix becomes sufficiently large to cause the crack to proceed again along one or more grain boundaries perpendicular to the applied load assisted by Mode II displacement.

Mode II displacements also accounted for wedging on the crack at the large bend shown in Figure 4 at “B” with the two crack surfaces becoming increasingly misaligned. Figure 4 also shows the growth of the crack through the matrix along the grain boundaries

Figure 4. Progress of cracks along grain boundaries through the matrix at elevated temperature for the Comral-85 composite.

Debonding at particle “E” results in the crack deflected to the interface. The joined particles to the right have already debonded and the matrix ligament between them and “E” final tears. the crack eventually follows the grain boundaries down to particle “F”. Thus, although it might appear that the crack would travel straight down between particles “C” and “E” the debonding of particles in the process zone has controlled the crack path.

Indeed debonding can be seen to the left as well along the path from “G” to “H”. Microcracking at “H” eventually leads to crack growth into that region. At this stage there are 3 cracks growing as shown in Figure 5. This also shows the amount of deformation and damage just prior to failure. Microcracking at grain boundaries and particle-matrix interfaces is prevalent along with what appears to be lifting of grains and particles. The level of deformation in the matrix is higher than that of the ambient specimens. The lowering of the yield stress and elastic modulus with increase in temperature could affect this deformation as could any creep mechanisms due to the slow cycle rate.

Grain boundaries were also observed to “open up” ahead of the crack tip and was not evident in the room temperature *in situ* samples. Just prior to failure out-of-plane distortion was observed. Grains and particles were observed to lift up out of the specimen plane. Microcracks ahead of the main crack were seen to grow in both directions as well as cracks at the debonded interfaces. Crack branching along grain boundaries oblique to the main crack

was observed and in some cases where significant crack opening occurred debris was seen to be moving about.

Figure 5. Low magnification photographs of Comral-85 at (a) minimum and (b) maximum loads, fatigued at 180°C.

GENERAL COMMENTS

It appears that the crack tends to grow along grain boundaries, this being particularly evident at the elevated temperatures. Generally intergranular failure suggests some form of creep mechanism or the presence of impurities at the grain boundaries. Creep-fatigue interactions have been documented and usually lead to intergranular cavitation. For aluminium alloys this mechanism has been observed at room and low temperatures. Creep may also be a result of the very low cycle rate in this test and may explain why, although deformation seemed greater at the elevated temperature for the in situ tests, little difference was found in the standard fatigue tests.

Furukawa et al. have investigated creep in the Comral material. Though not complete, their results show that the composite has a higher stress exponent (≈ 8.3 at 200°C) than the corresponding plane alloy. Mishra et al. reanalysed data on SiC reinforced 6061 alloy. They suggest that in these composites dislocations are generated at a grain boundary, travel across the grain and are absorbed by the other grain boundary.

Hadianfard et al. have confirmed the observations made here that the growth of fatigue cracks at the higher levels of ΔK occurs via the linkage of the main crack with microcracks ahead of the crack tip and particle debonding.

Using stereo-opsis the deformation behaviour around the crack tip was observed. A series of photographs were taken as the crack approached the particle and the strain response of the matrix was observed. The strain response represented by Mohr's circles is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Mohr circles of strain at (a) 57,000 cycles, (b) 58,000 cycles and (c) 59,500 cycles.

As the crack approaches the particle, though growth here is very small, and as damage accumulates two main points can be noted:

1. The shear strain between the crack tip and the particle does not increase significantly but does change orientation, tending to align with the interface;
2. The magnitude of the strain between the crack tip and the particle reduces.

The first point may explain why the observed behaviour of crack growth is to travel toward the side of the particle instead of straight on. Together with the second point of a lower strain at the top of the particle may explain the observed behaviour as shown and discussed in Figure 1(b). The crack eventually curves over to the right and down the matrix-particle interface.

CONCLUSION

Crack growth rates, on a microstructural scale, in this material are a function of the proximity of the crack tip to the particles. Away from the particles the crack grows faster than when it is near a particle. The crack deflection and wedging, caused by the particle, tends to slow the growth rate down. However, as the stress intensity at the crack tip increases, microcrack formation at the particle matrix interface, i.e. debonding, and along grain boundaries, mainly between closely spaced particles and their resultant linkage results in an increased overall growth rate.

The mechanisms observed at elevated temperatures were the same as those at room temperature though more pronounced. There appeared to be much more deformation within the matrix. This is due to the lower yield strength and stiffness at these elevated temperatures as well as the possibility of creep-fatigue interactions. This latter point is the subject of further studies. In both cases, crack growth occurred via particle debonding ahead of the crack tip and is associated with intergranular void formation and coalescence. This suggests that the matrix particle interface is weak and that either creep and/or grain boundary impurities are present.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Australian Research Council for partial support of this work. Thanks are also due to Dr Malcolm Couper of Comalco Research Centre, Thomastown, Australia, for the supply of Comral-85 for testing and Dr David Davidson of Southwest Research Institute, San Antonio, USA for the use of his testing and SEM facilities.

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